

SECURITY CHALLENGES FOR REMOTE WORKERS AS A RESULT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC SITUATION

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Abstract

Purpose – Identify the advantages and disadvantages along with the security vulnerabilities and security recommendations for remote working, related to organizations in various industries.

Methodology – Performed a literature review on various scientific articles and cyber security related websites, in order to identify the proposed elements.

Findings – Remote working approach involves significant financial savings for many organizations capable to offer this model, but even though, a new threat occurs, which relates to security vulnerabilities able to affect the wellbeing of both the organization and employees.

Research implications – During the research we gathered together elements that have proven tracking record and which involve various examples.

Value – Value added relates to a security recommendations list which could be used by organizations in order to secure their data.

Key words: remote work, cybersecurity, attacker.

Introduction

Due to evolution of technology, on different markets have emerged more and more remote working related opportunities that allow different companies from various industries to provide employees the chance of working from anywhere in the world. This type of job becomes ideal for digital employees who enjoy travelling the world, work from exotic places and having the freedom they've always dreamed about. Even though, many people prefer to work from their comfortable home and a remote job is ideal for this, as they are not imposed to comply with office hours, to the time lost during traveling from one place to another, some being stressed about the clothes that have to be different from one day to another and to allocate a specific budget on meals, transportation and other needs.

The main purpose of this research is to explore and understand the actions that Covid-19 has imposed to the companies from various industries, in order to develop research strategies related to information security issues and organizational behavior from a business perspective. Along with this, literature review is the methodology used to perform this research, that aims to highlight the advantages and disadvantages of remote working, along with the security issues and recommendations for this working approach.

The development and utility of this research will provide ideas for academic research and managers of companies from various industries, so that they can promote the importance of information security of the daily's handled data, in order to obtain a secure and comfortable workplace.

Advantages and disadvantages of remote working

Since the appearance of Covid-19 and its spread around the world, companies were obligated to force us to reinvent ourselves and turn crises into great opportunities (Buitrago, 2020). As per Miranda (2020) working from home became a way of permanent execution for some employees, that involves an employment contract carried out remotely, using various software and hardware systems. Therefore, the employer and the employee do not interact physically, the employee will not make any regular visits

at the employer's office, except when required for certain specific cases. As a result, working from home aims to move to a different reality, where using the software and hardware technology, the employer no longer has to ensure provisions regarding the execution of employment contract, while the worker is able to provide the agreed services in a well manner from home.

A great advantage of this approach relates to the savings up to 30 percentage in infrastructure, along with a higher level of employee satisfaction, as a result of the flexibility provided and a balance in between job responsibilities and personal life. O'Donnellan (2022) also states that 48 percentage of employees are working remotely in 2022, while before pandemic the percentage was around 30 percentage.

Figure 1. Projected Percentage of Employees Working Remotely, Before and After the Pandemic [5]

Main advantages of remote working could be listed as it follows:

- Possibility of working from home or anywhere in the world, if there is an approval from company that employee could leave the country;
- Family reconciliation, by spending more time with the members;
- Increased productivity, as a result of a lot of saved time and feeling comfortable at the home's desk;
- Costs savings, as not having to spend budget on transportation;
- Less stress and revitalized mindset (Kunsmann);
- No need for relocation if an active internet connection is available at home;
- Schedule flexibility, if the option of working at any hour is available;
- Fully comfortable work environment, being designed by the employee based on personal preferences;
- Fewer distractions, as the work environment could be isolated from family members (Ammons and Markham, 2004);
- Less sick days taken from work, as the health is easier to be carried out from home;
- Absence of office politics;

We understood that remote working offers various benefits for employees and cost savings for employers. But even though, before stepping into the remote working world, companies from various industries need to take in consideration the office culture, number of current employees and business goals.

The trend of working from anywhere in the world seems to be considered more and more by many organizations and individuals as becoming the future of work. Technology evolves day by day and it will continue providing us the chance to become virtually closer and closer, across different time zones and continents. Since employees are not physically present in the same office, using the advanced technology for work could reach same level of effectiveness, or could exceed the current level (www.wework.com).

As the remote working brought up many advantages for employees around the world, they also face many disadvantages from this approach and most important could be described as:

- Social and professional isolation, as the only interaction with other people is virtually (Toscano and Zappala, 2020);
- Missing of organization's cultural values (Harrington and Santiago, 2006);
- Longer working hours for individuals who are not able to keep workload balance (Flores, 2019);
- Increased sedentary life-style (Cheng, Chao and Gau, 2010);
- Hyper connection, since employees spend many hours in front of a computer;
- Postural problems and eye disorders for spending many hours on a chair;

Considering the aforementioned advantages and disadvantages, we observed that remote working has the potential to achieve the expected level of production for companies in various industries. However, it also proved that could be an extremely dangerous weapon due to the consequences that affects in a negative way both the employee and the organization. A negative aspect was observed on the emotional side of the employees, as the stress, anxiety, fear, etc. have led some of them to face the impossibility of handling this change, every day of working from home being associated with a continuous state of instability (www.prosalute.net).

Security disadvantages of remote working

Along with the aforementioned issues, another negative side the of virtual world has arisen, being related to cyber security. This is a crucial part for the financial stability and brand reputation of an organization, since all data could be compromised as a result of a successful cyber-attack from an attacker. Considering that the priority of this issue type is critical, during the research we also put together a list with the most important elements from a security disadvantages perspective, described as it follows:

- Social Engineering – attackers use psychological manipulation in order to obtain various sensitive information in the possession of the victim (www.imperva.com). By building trust in the victim, attackers could be able to reach to the point where are leading victims to provide sensitive information or install malicious software on their own;
- Online Scams and Phishing – is performed via e-mails, ads, or websites that the user regularly use. E.g., sender of the malicious e-mail pretends to be a legitimate organization, such as the bank and the related associated content warns that there is an issue with the account, most usually related to security. In order to resolve this issue, the victim is invited to click on a link, that could lead to a fictitious website developed and controlled by the attacker. Being difficult to notice the difference between the original website and the malicious one, victim enters personal details, giving them away to the attacker (www.cybersecurity360.it);
- Ransomware – is designed to forbidden the victims' access to their data, being afterwards blackmailed by attacker to pay an amount of money via cryptocurrency in order to obtain the data decryption key (Carlin, O'Kane and Sezerl, 2017);
- DoS and DDoS attacks – DoS is used to send a big amount of data packets to a server, flooding it in this way and making a website or another resource inoperative. Its successor, DDoS, includes the same actions as its predecessor, the only difference here being related to the number of machines used to flood the targeted system (www.fortinet.com);
- Improper Virtual Private Network (VPN) configuration – if a VPN is not secured, it could potentially expose the entire network of an organization to various security threats, as malware, DoS/DDoS attacks and spoofing attacks (Burluson-Davis, 2021);
- Vulnerabilities in videoconference software – if outdated version of a software is used for videoconferences, then an attacker could be able to access internal network of the company via various existing vulnerabilities' exploits (Palmer, 2019).
- Use of a weak password – if a password policy for login on Wi-Fi, operating system, VPN or other resources is not enforced, this would make easier for an attacker to perform a brute force attack and obtain the credentials;
- Access sensitive data through unsafe Wi-Fi network – if an user connects to a public network and is not aware of who configured its security, then without using a proper VPN, the data transmitted in between client and host could be eavesdropped;

- Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) for work – without a strictly and proper security policy implemented for using employees' own devices at work, this could lead to various issues, as sensitive data theft, malware spread in the company's network and last but not least brand reputation could be affected (www.n-able.com).

Now that we briefly described the most common vulnerabilities of remote working, we can understand that for this new model, beside the advantages it provides, it comes up with some various vulnerabilities that may affect both employee's and organization's wellbeing. In this way, both parties should always take in consideration the worst-case scenario when it comes to cyber security vulnerabilities and should pay attention on keeping network and data secure all the time, through implementing and making use of many available technologies.

Security recommendations for remote working

During our research, we gathered together the most important elements when we talk about security recommendations for remote working. For this, we created two categories with the related elements, one for the employees and the other one for organizations, as the followings:

1. For employees

- Implementing a strong password policy and, in this way, setting up a strong password will make it difficult for an attacker to perform a brute force attack (www.timelyapp.com);
- Installing regular updates will ensure that all vulnerabilities' patches containing the related fixes are applied to various software solutions (www.timelyapp.com);
- Being vigilant regarding phishing campaigns and reporting these incidents to organization's security team (www.timelyapp.com);
- Locking the device when leaving the desk will protect against any unauthorized access to company's information (www.timelyapp.com);
- Family members shall stay away from work devices, in order to e.g., avoid any access to the internet for personal reasons, performing unexpected actions, etc. (www.kaspersky.com);
- Secure home Wi-Fi, that will make difficult for an attacker to access it and obtain access to the connected devices (www.kaspersky.com);

2. For organizations

- Identity and Access Management (IAM) Solution provides organizations with protection for their employees and data, diminishing expenses and guaranteeing regulatory compliance (McDade, 2022);
- Endpoint security solutions have the capabilities of preventing and fighting against file-based malware, detecting and blocking malicious behavior of various deployed applications and generate reports containing extracted data, that could be further used to respond to security incidents and alerts (www.trellix.com);
- Zero-trust network access is composed from a security model able to monitor and authenticate each network access attempt (www.cisco.com);
- Data loss prevention is a set of various software solutions and agreed security processes used to ensure that sensitive data of an organization is not lost or accessed by attackers (De Groot, 2022);
- User behavioral analytics is a process used to analyze the patterns of an employee's behavior in order to discover potential threats (www.wikipedia.com);
- Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) requires employees to provide multiple credentials in order to access a system (Malik, 2021);
- Least privilege access is a security model which states that an employee should only be able to access the systems needed to complete the related tasks and if the employee does not need an access right, then the access should not be provided (www.wikipedia.org);

- h. Use of a password manager in order to save all systems' passwords in one encrypted place, so that employee will not have to use similar or weak passwords to remember them;
- i. Encrypt the devices, so if one is lost or stolen, attacker won't be able to access the data;
- j. Use of a strong VPN solution that will encrypt the communication between client and server and redirect it to secure servers until data reach destination;
- k. Implement an antivirus software in order to continuous scan for different forms of malware while navigating the internet, opening an attachment, inserting an USB drive, installing a new software, etc.;
- l. Implement a firewall solution that will check every incoming and outgoing connections;

With the aforementioned security recommendations for both employees and organizations, we can understand that in order to reduce the risks and vulnerabilities for organizations in various industries, there are many aspects that have to be considered, from user behavior to various hardware and software security systems. In short, these are some of the best approaches in order to establish a good security posture of an organization and not suffer any type of problem that could compromise its data privacy.

Conclusions

In conclusion, since the Covid-19 pandemic came across the world, organizations from various industries started on betting remote working as an alternative way to perform the related activities. We observed that this new approach could mean significant financial savings for all the stakeholders and the related work activity could be maintained without putting the life of the employees at risk, since they don't have to leave their home. In this way, some advantages as the work-life balance or increased productivity worth to be mentioned, but in the same time, organizations face new threats that have to be properly managed.

Mainly, we highlighted the information security vulnerabilities and ways of protecting against them and concluded that in order to accomplish these, organizations have to combine clearly defined policies for handling the data and the use of adequate software solutions that provides the management of its security. Even so, a proper security awareness training has to be provided to employees annually, containing new threats to computer systems and ways of combating them. Along with all these recommended security software technologies, we conclude that each employee must be responsible for his actions and for the consequences of the performed actions while working from home.

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